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Dissipative CLT-Based Seismic Upgrading System for RC-Framed Structures: Experimental Characterization, Numerical Modelling, and Design Guidelines

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates a seismic retrofit technique named e-CLT, which is part of the solution for integrated seismic and energy rehabilitation of buildings developed in the framework of the research project e-SAFE funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. According to this technique, the RC structure is clad by means of CLT panels equipped with friction dampers, to increase lateral stiffness, strength, and energy dissipation capacity. The effectiveness of the e-CLT system has been proved by a full-scale experimental test. A finite element numerical model of the RC frame with e-CLT system has been developed and calibrated based on the experimental results. Hence, guidelines for the design of seismic strengthening of multi-storey RC framed building structures by e-CLT system have been drawn based on the results of a parametric analysis conducted on a set of RC case study frames representative of a variety of existing buildings not designed for seismic resistance.

1 | Introduction

In the second half of 20th century, reinforced concrete (RC) structures spread worldwide. However, most of these buildings predate modern code provisions, both in terms of structural and energy requirements. In Europe, more than 75% of the land is occupied by residential buildings and more than 40% of these are multi-storey RC framed structures constructed before the 1960s of the 20th century [1]. These structures are expected to exhibit poor seismic response, and their energy performance is so inadequate that they are liable for 36% of the total energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in Europe [2]. An explicative example of this issue is offered by the Italian territory. According to the latest census of Italian residential buildings [3], more than 70% of the

current residential buildings were realized before 1981, when seismic zonation included only 25% of the Italian territory. These buildings suffer from high seismic vulnerability, as dramatically demonstrated by recent seismic events [4, 5]. In addition, almost 90% of the Italian building stock was constructed before 1991, that is, before the enforcement of the first regulation on thermal performance criteria [6]. To boost a compelling transition toward a resilient and sustainable society, European regulations on construction work [7] have been adding requirements to keep the construction performances intact and extend its service life as long as possible [8]. Therefore, the rehabilitation of these buildings is a real need and, as a matter of fact, during the last 30 years the rate of retrofit interventions increased from 20% to 40% and it is expected that this trend will steadily increase in the near future.

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Conventional uncoupled rehabilitation techniques aim to enhance the seismic performance or the thermal one [9]. Furthermore, the majority of the conventional techniques require the addition of devices that occupy space for installation, need invasive installing work that force relocation of occupants and cause activities disruption. Hence, new approaches are required to promote environmental economic-social sustainable energy and seismic retrofit interventions. Among the integrated approaches currently under development, the “double skin” approach is one of the most promising. It consists of the superimposition of a second external structure designed to enhance seismic and thermal performance of the building. The main advantage of this solution is that its installation takes place from the outside of the building, thus reducing to the minimum the disruption or the disturbance to occupants. Different construction techniques and materials have been proposed for the second skin. For example, Takeuchi et al. [10] developed a steel dissipative façade, Marini et al. [11] proposed a second skin with steel shear walls and the possibility of introducing dissipative members, Ferrante et al. [12] investigated an integrated solution based on steel exoskeleton. RC second skin has been developed as well, such as the new RC infilled frame connected to the existing structure proposed by Manfredi and Masi [9] or the cast-in-site RC frame system endowed with EPS modules developed by Pozza et al. [13]. An alternative approach is followed by Bournas [14], who proposes the use of Textile Reinforced Mortar jackets to increase the out-of-plane load capacity and the energy absorption capacity of infill walls in RC frames.

In the ride toward the ecofriendly materials, the use of wood as a structural material has recently gained prominence. In particular, cross-laminated timber (CLT) is a sustainable solid wood-based construction material with low mass and excellent structural performance. CLT panels consist of an odd number of stacked crosswise layers of softwood boards, bonded by structural adhesive [15], that can sustain loads in all directions [16]. CLT panels are produced to a high degree of prefabrication, allowing efficient on-site installation. Notwithstanding the lightweight nature of CLT, it is characterized by a high in-plane lateral stiffness and strength. Furthermore, the possibility of combining CLT panels with ductile joints makes the use of CLT appealing in earthquake-prone areas [17, 18]. Thanks to these features, the use of CLT panels has been recently extended to seismic retrofit of RC existing structures, basically following the second skin approach already mentioned. Stazi et al. [19] proposed the encasement of CLT panels within the RC frame bays, as a replacement of masonry infills. Diagonal tests were conducted on confined and not confined CLT panels, while the effect of the CLT panels on RC structures was numerically investigated on a single-storey one-bay RC frame. Also, Smirolto et al. [20] proposed to replace the existing masonry infill of RC frames with a CLT panel, which was inserted into the frame and fixed to RC members by a timber sub-frame. The timber sub-frame and the RC frame are connected by concrete screws, which are designed to remain elastic. The ductile component of the system is the connection between the timber panel and timber sub-frame. The proposed technique was investigated by pushover analysis on single-bay single-storey frames and the numerical results showed an increase in terms of lateral resistance and maximum displacements. Although both studies demonstrated the good performances provided by the CLT

infills, in real existing structures the insertion of the CLT panels in place of infill walls would require quite large demolishing work and a not negligible disturbance to occupants. In this regard, Smirolto et al. [21] conducted an experimental study on an RC frame to introduce a less invasive option, i.e., CLT panels are applied to the building façade, without removing the masonry infills, and fastened to the outer face of RC beams by dowel-type connectors. However, the experimental tests evidenced that also this external configuration requires quite invasive works on the masonry infill panels, which must be cut to avoid interaction between RC columns and the walls. Furthermore, the dowel-type connectors transferred the shear force from the CLT panel to the columns, which mainly sustained the damage mechanism. Sustersic and Dujic proposed the combination of CLT panels with a “nano” insulation layer to create an outer shell that is connected to the existing structure by steel anchor brackets [22]. The technique was experimentally tested on a two-storey one-bay RC frame with masonry infills and numerically investigated on a three-storey two-bay RC frame [23–25]. The dissipative capacity is delegated to the steel angular brackets. However, it is stated that such a connection would require modifications to be applicable in real structures. Indeed, it requires access from the inside of the building [22]. Badini et al. [26] proposed the use of CLT walls perpendicularly to the façade. The wall is connected to the RC frame by steel brackets, while post-tensioned steel tendons are introduced between CLT panels to increase the dissipative capacity. However, the impact of the forces transmitted by the external structure to the existing RC members may imply the reduction of the capacity of RC members and the need for additional internal local interventions.

In this framework, this paper proposes an innovative integrated seismic and energy system, named e-CLT. The concept of this system was drafted in [27] and its development as a seismic upgrading tool is part of the multidisciplinary Horizon 2020 innovation research project e-SAFE (energy and seismic Affordable rEnovation solutions) [28]. This paper presents the research activity of this project in the field of seismic upgrading and the related outcomes. The e-CLT system is based on the idea of endowing existing RC-framed buildings with a second performing skin made of pre-assembled and customizable components. The e-CLT system is composed of prefabricated CLT panels superimposed to the external wall and connected to the RC beams by friction dampers. Each damper connects the CLT panels of two consecutive floors to the intermediate RC beams and consists of two steel profiles: the anchor profile is connected to the RC beam by anchor bolts and to the other profile, named free profile, by slotted holes and pretensioned high-strength bolts. The free profile receives the shear force from the CLT panel placed above and transmits it to the anchor profile by means of the friction exerted on the contact surface. The components of the damper are shaped so as to decouple the CLT panel’s vertical movements from those of the dampers.

In case of a seismic event, two possible scenarios may occur: If the seismic action is moderate, the dampers rigidly connect the CLT panels to the RC structure, thus making available additional lateral stiffness and strength. This is helpful to avoid damage in non-structural components. On the other hand, if strong seismic actions occur, the dampers activate and dissipate part of the input seismic energy by sliding. This reduces the damage of

structural components and prevents the building from collapsing. It is noteworthy that the activation of the dampers defines an upper bound to the force sustained by the CLT panels, thus preventing their failure even in case of unexpectedly strong ground motions. The e-CLT system presents several advantages with respect to other systems. The e-CLT panels can be combined with non-structural pre-assembled panels made of lightweight wooden frames and provided with high-performing windows. The e-CLT system is designed to allow a quick and easy external installation, which can be performed by mobile lifting equipment, thus avoiding costs and time needed for the scaffolding set-up. Different parts of the system, such as anchor profiles, are suitable for pre-assembly process off site. Furthermore, since the installation process takes place from the outside, the disturbance to occupants is minimized and operativity disruption is avoided. The damper, considering its size, is suitable for installation on most common RC framed buildings. Furthermore, it is installed outside the building and the damper inspection and maintenance are also eased by string courses, which can be easily removed.

Compared to studies available in the literature, the paper has a twofold innovative goal: on one hand, to demonstrate and quantify the benefits provided by the e-CLT system to the structural response of an RC frame, based on experimental tests; on the other hand, to assess the impact of the e-CLT system on the structural performance of a set of realistic RC buildings, by means of finite element numerical models and incremental nonlinear dynamic analysis (IDA). To this end, the research followed three main steps: (1) the effect of the e-CLT system on the seismic response of RC frames was experimentally reproduced, (2) a reliable numerical model of the RC frame with e-CLT system was developed, and (3) the seismic performance of multi-storey RC frames with different e-CLT configurations was investigated, so as to provide guidelines for the design of seismic upgrading by e-CLT. First, the results of two quasi-static cyclic tests carried out on two infilled RC frames (without and with e-CLT), are presented. The tests characterized the cyclic response of the structural system and provided data for the calibration of numerical model. In particular, the availability of two tests allowed the calibration of the numerical models of the RC frame and the e-CLT system in two steps. To extend the study to actual buildings with RC framed structures designed according to old (non-seismic) regulations, a set of multi-storey RC frame models is defined. Incremental dynamic analyses and pushover analyses are carried out on these frame models to investigate the seismic deficiencies of existing RC-framed buildings and the capability of pushover analysis in detecting such deficiencies. Hence, IDAs are carried out on the RC frame models equipped with e-CLT. Three different configurations of e-CLT are considered: the local narrow configuration, the local extended configuration, and the spread configuration. The results of IDA led to identifying the most effective configuration, relating it to the outcome of pushover analysis (design analysis), and quantifying the benefits that can be gained by e-CLT. In the numerical investigation, both ductile and fragile failure modes of structural members are checked. The seismic performance of the models is analyzed in terms of the distribution of seismic demand and demand-to-capacity ratio along the height, fragility curves, and mean annual frequency of exceedance of Near Collapse and Significant Damage limit states. The final section draws the design provisions for the seismic upgrading of RC structures by e-CLT.

2 | Experimental Testing of the e-CLT System

The experimental campaign is carried out at the CIRI-EC laboratory of the University of Bologna and is devoted to (1) characterizing the cyclic response of a masonry infilled RC frame strengthened by the e-CLT technology and (2) providing physical evidence that the components of the seismic upgrading system perform as intended, even after repeated and severe cycles of loading. To this end, two RC frame specimens were tested in real scale, in both unstrengthened and strengthened configurations, under quasi-static cyclic loading.

2.1 | Specimen Description

Two identical one-storey–one-bay RC frames are tested in the two investigated configurations. The RC frames replicate the typical constructive features of Italian buildings of the '70s and are designed in compliance with the building code enforced in 1974 [29] considering gravity loads only. Details on the design of the RC frames may be found in [30]. The span length is equal to 4.0 m and the inter-storey height is 3.2 m. Columns have 300 × 300 mm cross section, while a 300 × 400 mm cross section is adopted for beam. The RC frames are infilled with a single layer 120-mm-thick masonry wall realized with extruded hollow blocks and aligned with an external surface of the frame (Figure 1a). Compression tests were performed on cube and cylinder samples collected during the cast phase of the two frames. The average values of the cylinder compressive strength of strengthened and unstrengthened frames are 21.9 and 21.4 MPa, respectively. Tensile tests were run on three steel rebar specimens collected from the steel lot and the average yielding strength was equal to 534.6 MPa. The e-CLT system was constituted by a 100 mm thick CLT panel (5 layers of 20 mm thickness) connected to the RC frame by means of a steel apparatus (Figure 1b). The two upper components of the steel apparatus are anchored to the upper RC beam and support the CLT panel, while the two bottom components are mechanical friction dampers activated by the relative displacement between CLT panel and bottom RC beam.

2.2 | Experimental Setup and Test Protocol

A specifically designed setup is developed to carry out quasi-static tests of the two specimens (Figures 1 and 2). The RC frame is anchored to the strong floor while a horizontal displacement is imposed to the top RC beam by means of a 500 kN MTS servo-hydraulic jack anchored to the concrete reaction wall. The anchoring system of the bottom RC beam is realized by rigid steel brackets and post-tensioned dywidag bars and virtually avoids also the horizontal sliding of the RC frame over the strong floor. Furthermore, the steel brackets aligned on the RC columns serve as a fastening system for the vertical bars used to apply the axial force to the columns. The axial force, equal to 250 kN, is applied to each column by means of hydraulic jacks placed over them and constrained by transverse steel beams fastened to the bottom brackets described before. The vertical load application system is designed with rod end pins and conical nuts, which allow cyclic large displacements in the horizontal direction. The applied vertical forces reproduce the axial force caused by the

FIGURE 1 | Geometry and photos of specimens: (a,c) unstrengthened and (b,e) infilled strengthened RC frame, (d) members cross sections.

FIGURE 2 | Test setup: (a) global scheme and (b) photo of laboratory testing system (strengthened configuration).

gravity load for the seismic design situation in the first storey columns of a three-storey residential building. The horizontal displacement application system is composed of a steel tie made up of stiffened transverse steel plates placed at the two ends of the upper RC beam and connected through post-tensioned dywidag bars. The servo-hydraulic actuator is connected to one end of the tie and is constrained to the reaction wall. The entire test system is transversally stabilized by means of a lattice steel system allowing for the horizontal and vertical displacements only of the top RC beam through spherical rollers. This transverse stabilization system avoids possible out-of-plane displacement of the RC frame, in particular in the case of the strengthened

configuration, with the e-CLT panel eccentrically fixed with respect to the horizontal force alignment.

The measurement system depicted in Figure 2 is composed of: (1) two horizontal transducers recording the base displacement (LVDT 1) and the top displacement (LVDT 2) respectively; (2) a horizontal transducer recording the relative displacement between the friction damper and the base RC beam (LVDT 3) and (3) a LOAD CELL recording the force in the actuator. The RC frame drift is calculated as the difference between the horizontal displacements of the top and base RC beams recorded during the test using LVDT 2 and LVDT 1, respectively. Moreover,

TABLE 1 | Horizontal loading protocol.

Step of loading	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Drift amplitude (mm)	±1	±2	±4	±8	±16	±24	±32	±48	±64	±80	±96
Drift ratio (%)	±0.03	±0.06	±0.13	±0.25	±0.50	±0.75	±1.00	±1.50	±2.00	±2.50	±3.00
Loading rate (mm/s)	0.02	0.05	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.70	1.00	1.20
No. of cycles	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3

FIGURE 3 | Cyclic response of the unstrengthen and strengthen frames: (a) load-drift hysteresis loops, (b) RC drift versus e-damper sliding, (c) dissipated energy.

the friction damper sliding is recorded for the strengthened configuration using LVDT 3. Figure 2 shows a comprehensive scheme of the setup and a photo of the experimental equipment.

The specimens are loaded in two phases: first, the vertical forces are applied and gradually increased up to the target value of 250 kN in force control, then the horizontal displacement is cyclically applied. In the second phase, the vertical forces are kept constant, by controlling the hydraulic pressure of the jacks, while drift cycles of increasing amplitude are applied by controlling the difference in the horizontal displacements of the upper and lower beams. During the entire cyclic loading phase, the force in the actuator is measured using the LOAD CELL. The horizontal loading protocol is designed taking into account the displacement capacity of the e-CLT system. It is summarized in Table 1, which lists drift amplitude, drift ratio, loading rate, and a number of cycles for each step of the cyclic loading.

2.3 | Test Results

All the components of the e-CLT system behaved as intended, up to the end of the test. Indeed, the CLT panel remained elastic and did not experience instability or any kind of local damage even under the largest imposed drift, that is, 3% of the storey height. Hence, it efficiently transferred the horizontal force from the top beam to the two friction dampers at the bottom of the panel. The dampers activated as planned under the push exerted by the CLT panel and slid alternatively back and forward dissipating energy. At the end of the test, the steel apparatus was dismantled and the single components (plates, screws, bolts, and aluminum shim layers) were accurately examined. No sign of yielding or other type of damage was detected, thus proving that the steel apparatus

and fastening system behaved elastically for the whole duration of the test.

Figure 3a compares the load-drift hysteresis loops obtained for the unstrengthened (red line) and strengthened (black line) configuration. It is evident that the RC frame with the e-CLT system exhibits initial lateral stiffness and peak strength significantly larger than those of its unstrengthened counterpart. Moreover, the strength degradation (i.e., difference between the force achieved at the 1st and the 3rd repeated cycles) results generally lower for the strengthened configuration, especially for large drift levels. Figure 3b shows the slippage between the two parts of the friction damper versus the drift of the RC frame recorded during the test. A variation of the RC frame drift while the damper slippage remains constant (vertical branches in the graph) identifies a reversal of loading. This occurs when the force transmitted by the CLT panel to the damper temporarily becomes lower than the damper friction force and the variation of the slippage stops. After the reversal, when the force in the damper attains again the value of the friction force, both drift and slippage start varying simultaneously again. Hence, the height of the vertical branches of the graph represents the portion of the drift that cannot be transformed into slippage because of the deformability of the panel and of the friction damper fastening system. The small height of the vertical branches of the graph observed in Figure 3b demonstrates that a 100-mm-thick CLT panel is stiff enough to transform almost the whole drift into slippage (about 80%, since for drift slightly lower than 100 mm the slippage is about 80 mm), thus forcing the dampers to dissipate energy efficiently. This results in a big positive impact of the e-CLT system on the energy dissipation capacity (computed according to [31]). Indeed, the area enclosed by the hysteresis loops (dissipated energy) of the strengthened frame is much larger than that of the unstrengthened frame (Figure 3a). The

FIGURE 4 | Description of elements of the numerical model.

comparison between the energy dissipated at the end of each loading step by the strengthened and unstrengthened frames (Figure 3c) quantifies the improvement of dissipation capacity provided by e-CLT, which can be even 200% of that of the unstrengthened frame.

3 | Numerical Model of the Test Specimen

A plane numerical model of the test specimen is implemented in OpenSees [32] and developed into two “macro-systems”: the infilled RC frame and the e-CLT system (Figure 4). Each part of the numerical model is first described, and then the values of mechanical parameters are calibrated so that the cyclic response of the numerical model matches the experimental one.

3.1 | Description of the Numerical Model

The numerical model of the infilled RC frame includes columns, beams, and infill panels, and it is assumed fixed to the ground. For RC columns and beams, nonlinear behavior is supposed to be limited to plastic hinge regions at member ends, while the remaining part of the element remains elastic. They are modeled as *beamWithHinges element* with the modified Gauss Radau integration rule [33]. The length of plastic hinge L_{pl} is set equal to the depth of the cross section and the cross-section over L_{pl} is discretized into fibers. Specifically, the concrete part of the cross-section is subdivided into fibers having 5 mm depth and width equal to the width of the cross-section, while single fibers are used to model rebars. The Kent–Scott–Park constitutive law (*Concrete01 uniaxialMaterial*) [34] and the elastic–plastic constitutive law with kinematic hardening (*Steel02 uniaxialMaterial*) [32] are assigned to the concrete and the steel fibers, respectively. A pair of diagonal trusses is used to model the infill panel. Under the effect of horizontal forces, only the compressive branch is active, while the tensile one provides a minimal non-zero stiffness necessary for numerical stability. Although this modeling approach of infill panels is rather simple, it is recognized to reproduce satisfactorily the global response of frames under horizontal forces and is deemed an acceptable compromise between computational burden and accuracy of results [35]. As proposed by Panagiotakos and Fardis [36] and Celarec et al. [37], the force-displacement relationship of the diagonal trusses is determined to replicate the shear force-drift relationship of the infill panel. This relationship consists of four branches: the first branch corresponds to the linear elastic behavior up to the first cracking of the infill, the second branch runs from the first cracking up to the maximum strength, the third branch is the post-capping degrading branch, and runs from the maximum strength to the residual strength, finally, the fourth branch is

horizontal and corresponds to the residual strength. For each branch, the values of stiffness and maximum force are determined according to the equations proposed in [37]. The abovementioned multilinear force-displacement relationship is converted into an equivalent stress–strain relationship. The values of stress–strain couples of the three corners of the envelope, both in the positive and negative loading direction, are assigned to the trusses by the *Pinching4 uniaxialMaterial* implemented in OpenSees.

The e-CLT system is composed of the CLT panel and friction dampers (Figure 4). The CLT panel is modeled by means of six equivalent trusses: two vertical trusses, two horizontal trusses, and two diagonal trusses (Figure 5). All trusses are elastic and have cross-section with the unitary area. The axial stiffness of the trusses is calibrated to provide the same in-plane stiffness of the CLT panel. To this end, the elastic modulus of the vertical and diagonal trusses E_c and E_d are calibrated so that the horizontal and the vertical displacements of the truss model are equal to those of the actual CLT panel subjected to two horizontal forces applied on the top corners of the panel (Figure 5). Consistently, the elastic modulus of the horizontal trusses E_b is calibrated so that the horizontal displacement of the CLT panel simulated by trusses is equal to that of the actual CLT panel subjected to two opposite horizontal forces applied on top of the panel (Figure 5). The displacement demands of the actual CLT panel are determined by a second “support” numerical model, which simulates only the CLT panel by a single shell element with elastic orthotropic material. The Young and shear moduli in the three mutually perpendicular directions of the shell elements depend on the mechanical characteristics of the considered CLT panel.

Friction dampers are simulated by zero-length elements located at the beam-to-column intersection (Figure 4). The behavior of friction dampers in the horizontal direction is described by an elastic-plastic behavior (*Steel01 uniaxialMaterial* in OpenSees), whose yielding strength represents the friction force that activates the dampers. In the vertical direction, the damper can move freely.

The concentrated gravity loads on columns are those applied during the experimental test and are equal to 250 kN. The horizontal loading application system of the experimental test is simulated by a truss element with steel elastic modulus and cross-section area equal to that of the steel tie used in the test. The truss connects two additional external nodes that are formally coincident with the RC beam ends. Each additional node is connected to the corresponding node of the beam end by a zero-length element that reacts only in compression with very large axial stiffness. Two opposite horizontal forces equal to 320 kN are applied at each end of the beam to replicate the prestress force applied in the test.

FIGURE 5 | Evaluation of the axial stiffness of equivalent trusses simulating the CLT panel.

FIGURE 6 | Experimental versus numerical cyclic response of the unstrengthened frame in terms of total base shear-top displacement: (a) sub-component approach, (b) numerical model of RC frame (large amplitude displacements); (c) numerical model of RC infilled frame (low amplitude displacements).

3.2 | Calibration of the Parameters of the Numerical Model

To calibrate the mechanical features of the described numerical model, the results provided by the experimental test, in terms of base shear and top displacement, are assumed as targets. Two calibration processes are followed in series: First, the characteristics of the RC frame and the infill panel are determined based on the results of the cyclic test on the infilled RC frame (without e-CLT system). Afterward, the features of the e-CLT components are calibrated to match the experimental results of the strengthened specimen (with e-CLT).

In the first calibration process, the mechanical characteristics of both RC members (columns and beams) and infill panels are deduced from the same experimental test, following a “sub-component” approach (Figure 6a). This approach is based on the experimental observation that, for large displacement demand, the stiffness and strength of the infill panel drastically decrease in almost all RC framed structures subjected to horizontal forces. This allowed the determination of the mechanical parameters of

the RC members assuming as target the cyclic response under the largest displacement amplitudes, when the stiffness and strength of the infill panel has become negligible. In this step, the numerical model includes only the RC members and the maximum compression strength of concrete F_{cm} is set equal to 21.65 MPa, i.e., the mean compressive strength obtained from the concrete compressive coupon tests. The corresponding Young’s modulus E_{cm} is calculated as $2F_{cm}/\epsilon_{c2}$ and it is equal to 21950 MPa. However, to take into account the effect of concrete cracking, the moment of inertia of the section is reduced to 50% and 80% of I_g for beams and columns, respectively [38]. The confinement effect on the core of the member cross sections is neglected because the specimen is representative of RC structures designed without seismic provisions, that generally have few stirrups. The strains at maximum compression strength ϵ_{c0} and at crushing strength ϵ_{cu} are assumed equal to the conventional values 2×10^{-3} and 3.5×10^{-3} , respectively. The residual concrete compressive strength is calibrated based on the results of the full-scale experimental test carried out on the RC frame and set equal to 6 MPa, about 30% of the peak value. The tension strength of concrete is virtually zero. As for steel, Young’s modulus E_s is assumed equal to

TABLE 2 | List of parameters of numerical model.

Concrete 01	Steel 02
Maximum concrete compression strength $F_{cm} = 21.59$ MPa Young modulus $E_{cm} = 21950$ MPa strain at maximum compression strength $\epsilon_{c2} = 0.002$ strain at crushing strength $\epsilon_{cu} = 0.0035$ Residual concrete compressive strength = 6 MPa	Yielding strength $F_{ym} = 400$ MPa Young modulus $E_s = 210,000$ MPa Kinematic hardening ratio $b = 0.001$
Infill panel (Pinching 04)	
Thickness $t_w = 120$ mm Young modulus $E_w = 1979.7$ MPa Shear modulus $G_w = 791.9$ MPa Cracking strength 0.23 MPa Post-capping degrading stiffness parameter $\alpha = 0.035$ Residual strength parameter $\beta = 0.02$	Floating points defining the reloading of the cyclic response: $rDispP = 0.5, rForceP = 0.5, uForceP = 0, rDispN = 0,$ $rForceN = 0, uForceN = 0$ Floating points controlling the cyclic degradation: $g_{K1}, g_{K2}, g_{K3},$ $g_{K4}, g_{KLim} = 1; g_{D1} g_{D2} g_{D3} g_{D4} g_{DLim} = 0, g_{F1} g_{F2} g_{F3} g_{F4} g_{FLim} = 0.5$
Equivalent trusses for CLT	Friction dampers (Steel 02)
Elastic modulus of diagonal truss $E_d = 13840.3$ MPa Elastic modulus of vertical truss $E_c = 172423.5$ MPa Elastic modulus of horizontal truss $E_b = 329436.1$ MPa	Yield strength (activation force) 25.7 MPa Horizontal stiffness = 299.6 kN/m Vertical and rotational stiffnesses = 0.0

210,000 MPa while the yielding strength f_{ym} is equal to 400 MPa. The kinematic hardening ratio b is set equal to 0.001, while no isotropic hardening is present. Based on the match with the experimental results of the RC frame, the value of the yielding strength is assumed lower than that provided by the coupon test. This strategy allowed the numerical model to take into account the strength degradation caused by the instability of longitudinal rebars that occurred during the experimental test at large displacement demand. These parameters led to the cyclic response plotted in Figure 6b by the red line, which is in quite good agreement with the experimental response (black line) after the complete crushing of infills.

Once the mechanical parameters of the RC members have been determined, the numerical model is integrated with the equivalent diagonal trusses simulating the infill panel. In this second step, the features of the infill panel are determined so that the numerical model matches the experimental response when low-medium displacement amplitudes are applied, and the infill panel has not been significantly damaged yet. The mechanical properties are assigned according to the data provided by the experimental tests. Hence, the thickness is equal to 120 mm, Young's modulus and shear modulus are equal to 1979.7 and 791.9 MPa, respectively, while cracking strength is equal to 0.23 MPa. The parameters α and β , which rule the post-capping degrading stiffness and the residual strength, are calibrated to match the cyclic response of the infilled frame provided by the test, and values $\alpha = 0.035$ and $\beta = 0.02$ are found. Since the experimental results of the infilled frame showed cyclic degradation of strength and stiffness under cyclic loading, the values of the floating points defining the loading/reloading of the *Pinching4 uniaxialMaterial* are reported in Table 2.

The second calibration process is devoted to the determination of the mechanical parameters of the trusses, simulating the CLT panel, and the friction dampers, so that the structural response provided by the numerical model is in accordance with the experimental results of the strengthened RC frame. With regards to the CLT panel, the elastic moduli E_d, E_c, E_b of the diagonal, vertical, and horizontal trusses are set equal to 13840.3, 172423.5, and 329436.1 MPa, respectively. These values were determined by scaling by 0.50 times the elastic modulus of the trusses that were equivalent to the tested CLT panel modeled by a shell element (C24 class). The latter was characterized by an elastic orthotropic behavior with elastic moduli equal to 6748, 4622, and 370 MPa in the X, Y, and Z directions, respectively. Figure 7a shows the relation between drift of the frame and sliding of the damper located at its base. It can be observed that the drift increases linearly with the displacement of the damper. The red and black lines show that the results provided by the numerical model and experimental test are in good agreement. As for the damper, the parameters that need to be defined are the yield strength of the elastoplastic material and its elastic modulus. The experimental test shows a quite asymmetric response of the damper subjected to the cyclic horizontal force, with a peak positive and negative strength equal to 29.44 and -22.04 kN, respectively. The yield strength assigned to the damper in the numerical model is set equal to 25.7 MPa, which is the average value between the positive and negative strengths provided by the test. The elastic modulus was calibrated so that the response of the numerical analysis fit that of the experimental test, and it is set equal to 299.6 kN/m. The responses of the damper provided by the experimental test and the numerical model are reported in Figure 7b, where the sliding of the damper has been plotted as a function of the total applied force. The two plots show that the numerical model is able to predict accurately the response of the experimental test.

FIGURE 7 | Comparison of experimental versus numerical cyclic response of the strengthened frame in terms of (a) top displacement versus sliding of the damper, (b) total force versus damper displacement, (c) total base shear versus top displacement demand, (d) dissipated energy.

Once the calibration of the parameters is concluded by checking the local response of CLT members and dampers, the entire numerical model is fully defined. A list of all the calibrated parameters is reported in Table 2. Hence, the global response in terms of base shear and top displacement of the frame is observed (Figure 7c). The seismic response of the strengthened frame is characterized by a peak of resistance, around 200 kN, and a very high elastic stiffness due to the infill. After the cracking of the infill panel, the stiffness and the lateral strength decrease and tend to those of the RC frame with CLT and dampers. The numerical model (red line) is able to estimate the peak strength and the elastic stiffness provided by the experimental test (black line) accurately as well as the cyclic response of the frame after cracking of the infills. Indeed, the calibrated numerical model can accurately predict the energy dissipated by the specimen during each cycle of imposed displacement, with a maximum error at the ending cycle lower than 13% (Figure 7d).

4 | Case Study Buildings

A set of case studies is defined to encompass RC-framed buildings characterized by structural features and seismic shortcomings common in the Mediterranean building stock. First, the procedure followed to design the RC members is presented and all the configurations of the case study buildings are detailed. Hence, the numerical model developed to analyze the case study is described.

4.1 | Design of Case Study Buildings

Since most of the existing RC buildings were constructed between the middle and the end of the 20th century, when seismic codes were not in force yet or seismic zonation was still under evolution, they are affected by different levels of seismic deficiencies.

Following this observation, first, a reference case study frame is designed for gravity loads only. This is representative of those buildings that were not originally conceived to face seismic forces but were afterward included in seismic-prone areas.

This building is five-storey high and has a rectangular plan layout (Figure 8) with dimensions equal to 28.8 and 15.5 m in the X - and Y -direction, respectively. The floor decks are realized by RC joists arranged along Y -direction connected by a 40 mm thick slab, and are supported by the four seven-bay frames orientated along the X -direction. Only two frames are disposed along the Y -direction, to close the perimeter of the plan layout. Since the majority of beams are disposed along the X -direction and columns oppose their strong inertia axis mainly along the X -direction, the lateral stiffness and strength along the X -direction are significantly larger than those along the Y -direction. Such a difference in the two directions of the building is a feature that often characterizes structures designed without seismic prescriptions. The distribution of lateral stiffness and strength is symmetric with respect to both axes passing through the geometric center of the plan layout, meaning that the structural response to horizontal seismic forces is purely translational.

Dead and live loads on structural elements are determined according to the nominal values provided in [39]. The allowable stress method is followed to size the cross sections and steel reinforcement of members, as prescribed by the Italian code enforced in 1974 [29]. Columns are designed considering axial force only, while beams are designed for bending moment and shear force. The internal axial force N of columns and the distributed loads resting on beams are evaluated according to the tributary area concept. The characteristic compressive cubic strength R_{ck} for concrete is equal to 25 MPa (corresponding to cylinder strength f_{ck} equal to 20 MPa for strength class C20/25). Steel grade Feb38K with a characteristic yield stress $f_{yk} = 375$ MPa

FIGURE 8 | Plan layout of the case study buildings and arrangement of infills in perimeter frames.

TABLE 3 | Cross section dimensions (in mm) of columns of the case study frame.

Storey	Columns							
	1, 8, 25, 32	2, 7, 26, 31	3, 6, 27, 30	4, 5, 28, 29	9, 16, 17, 24	10, 15, 18, 23	11, 14, 19, 22	12, 13, 20, 21
5	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300
4	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300
3	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 300	300 × 400	300 × 350	300 × 350
2	300 × 300	300 × 350	300 × 350	300 × 300	300 × 350	300 × 500	300 × 450	300 × 400
1	300 × 300	300 × 400	300 × 350	300 × 350	300 × 400	300 × 650	300 × 550	300 × 500

is used for reinforcement. Hence, values of the allowable stress of concrete and steel are equal to 8.5 and 215 MPa, respectively. The minimum area $A_{s,min}$ of the longitudinal rebars of columns is evaluated as the maximum between $0.006 A_{c,req}$ and $0.003 A_c$, where A_c is the actual cross-section area of concrete of the column. This design procedure leads to columns with decreasing cross-section area along the height (Table 3). Internal forces of beams are determined considering the scheme of continuous beams and the boundary schemes of single-span beams fixed at their ends. The cross-section of beams is equal to 300×600 mm at each storey. The minimum reinforcement assumed for the tension zone of beams is equal to 0.15% of the concrete cross-section. Stirrups with a diameter of 8 mm are used for beams and columns. The spacing of stirrups of beam ends is 150 or 200 mm depending on the design shear force and 300 mm in the central part. Instead, the spacing of columns is 180 mm and is derived by the application of minimal requirements given by the code.

Nowadays, infill panels are widely recognized to increase significantly the lateral strength and stiffness of the structure. Hence, neglecting infills' structural contribution in the analysis may cause misleading approximation in the structural assessment of the building. For this reason, three configurations of the unstrengthened case study building have been considered (Figure 8): The bare configuration represents structures with infill panels having such poor mechanical features that their structural contribution can be deemed negligible; the infilled configuration embodies one of the most common facade configurations, wherein spans with small (or no) openings are alternated to spans with large openings; the pilotis configuration is representative of buildings with extremely large openings at first storey (generally

due to a different destination use with respect to the upper storeys).

4.2 | Numerical Modeling of the Case Study Buildings

The response of the case study buildings is assessed twice considering the seismic excitation that acts separately in the X- and Y-direction. Since the building is symmetric in plan, a 2D numerical model, in compliance with that calibrated on the results of the experimental test and presented in Section 3, has been developed in OpenSees for the two directions. Thanks to the symmetry in plan, the numerical model is built to replicate half of the building. In particular, when seismic excitation is supposed to act along the X-direction, the response of the building is simulated by a numerical model that includes frames X1 and X2, while in case of forces along the Y-direction the four frames Y1 to Y4 are modeled. Considering that the building is quite different in terms of lateral stiffness and strength in the two directions, the two sets of frames are expected to return quite different seismic responses and performances, which double the number of analyzed case studies. Hereinafter, the two sets of frames are referred to as X-frame and Y-frame models.

The concrete slab at each level is assumed rigid in its own plane and is simulated by imposing that all the nodes of the same floor have the same horizontal displacement by means of *equalDOF* constraints. To take into account the P- Δ effect, a leaning column is added to the numerical model. A Rayleigh viscous damping is used and set at 5% for the first and the third modes of vibration.

The gravity loads assigned to beams and columns are those specified in EuroCode 8 (EC8) for the seismic design situation. The floor masses are equal to 220.4 t and are concentrated at the floor levels.

A member-by-member modeling is adopted for the analyzed frames. Columns and beams are modeled as *beamWithHinges elements* with fiber cross-section assigned to the plastic hinges. *Concrete01* and *Steel02 uniaxialMaterials* are the constitutive laws for concrete and steel fibers, respectively. The mechanical features are assigned in consistency with those used in the design. The confinement effect on the core of member cross-sections was neglected to replicate the lack of stirrups in concrete members of RC structures.

A *zeroLength element* is added at one end of each beam. This element connects the end of the beam to the corresponding node restrained by the rigid deck and is characterized by a large axial deformability. This expedient allows the beams to deform axially and avoids arising of axial force, which typically leads RC beams modeled by fiber elements to an artificial stiffening and strengthening [40]. Furthermore, large shear and flexural stiffnesses are assigned to the zeroLength element to transfer shear force and bending moment from the beam to the frame node.

Infills, CLT panels, and friction dampers, when present, are modeled by the technique shown in Section 3. The parameters that govern the response of these members as well as physical properties of masonry and wood are the same as used in Section 3. Finally, friction dampers are modeled as zeroLength elements with the previously calibrated mechanical features.

5 | Research Methodology

To assess the seismic performance of each case study frame, incremental nonlinear dynamic analyses are performed in the two directions in plan. A set of 30 artificial ground motions compatible with the EC8 elastic spectrum for soil type C, characterized by a 5% damping ratio and reference Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) for soil type A equal to 0.35 g, is adopted to simulate the seismic excitation with a return period $T_R = 475$ years. The duration of each accelerogram is 30.5 s. Hence, the PGA of the accelerograms is scaled from 0.05 g to 0.60 g in the step of 0.05 g. The results are analyzed in terms of (1) average response over the considered accelerograms, (2) fragility curves, and (3) mean annual frequency of exceedance of selected limit states.

The seismic response of the analyzed frames is investigated in terms of the heightwise distribution of the maximum storey drift demand Δ . Furthermore, the structural performance is evaluated by means of demand-to-capacity ratios (D/C) of columns and beams. The Near Collapse (NC) and the Significant Damage (SD) limit states are considered and the D/C ratios are evaluated in terms of shear force (V_{Ed}/V_{Rd}) and chord rotation (θ/θ_{NC}). The shear strength capacity is calculated according to EC2 [41]. The chord rotation capacity θ_{NC} is calculated according to equation A.1 of EC8-3 [42] for the NC limit state, while at the SD limit state θ_{SD} is determined as 75% of θ_{NC} . All structural members are assumed as primary members [42], hence the capacity is divided

by a coefficient γ_{el} equal to 1.5. The shear span is evaluated at each step of the analysis and no diagonal reinforcement is present. Since all members are assumed to lack modern construction details, the chord rotation capacity is decreased by 15% (as prescribed by EC8). Both the shear strength and chord rotation capacities are determined at each time step and compared to the corresponding demands. For a given excitation level, the maximum values of the response parameters (Δ or D/C) are evaluated for each ground motion and then averaged over the 30 inputs.

The results of the IDA are also used to determine the PGA leading to the attainment of the SD and NC limit states (PGA_{SD} or PGA_{NC}). For each Limit State (LS), two values of PGA are determined: the first one corresponds to the first attainment of the chord rotation capacity ($\theta/\theta_{LS} = 1$, ductile failure modes), the second one corresponds to the first attainment of the shear strength capacity ($V_{Ed}/V_{Rd} = 1$, fragile failure modes), among all columns and beams. When only ductile failure modes are considered, the PGA corresponding to the limit state is equal to the first value. If both ductile and fragile failure modes are taken into account, the PGA corresponding to the relevant limit state is assumed as the minimum between the first and second values. This approach permitted to evaluation of separately the effects of ductile and fragile failure modes on structural performance. The values of PGA_{SD} or PGA_{NC} are used to determine the fragility curves referred to as the exceedance of the SD and NC limit states. Both ductile and fragile failures are not explicitly accounted for in the numerical model but are checked in post-processing.

The fragility curve is defined by a lognormal cumulative distribution function [43] that describes the probability of exceedance of the limit state at different values of the intensity measure (IM), here assumed as PGA. The PGA corresponding to a 50% probability of exceedance of the relevant limit state is conventionally assumed as PGA capacity. The achieved performance is deemed adequate if the PGA capacity is not lower than the PGA stipulated by code.

Finally, the seismic performance of the case studies is also analyzed in terms of mean annual frequency of exceedance λ of the SD and NC limit states, which is calculated as

$$\lambda = \int_0^{\infty} p_{LS}(s) \cdot \left| \frac{d\bar{\lambda}_S(s)}{ds} \right| ds \cong \sum_{i=1}^n p_{LS}(s_i) |\Delta \bar{\lambda}_i| \quad (1)$$

where $p_{LS}(s)$ is the probability of exceedance of the considered limit state (fragility curve) and $\bar{\lambda}_S(s)$ is the probability of exceedance of the assigned PGA (mean seismic hazard curve). The mean seismic hazard function is determined by the following approach. Four different probabilities of exceedance P_{VR} (2, 10, 20, 50%) in a reference period of time of 50 years are considered. The return periods T_R corresponding to the above probabilities of exceedance and reference period of time are equal 72, 224, 475, and 2475 years [44]. The value of PGA corresponding to the return period of 475 years PGA^{475} is assumed equal to 0.35 g (high seismicity region). Hence, each PGA^{T_R} corresponding to the return period T_R is determined according to EC8-Part 1 [44] and the corresponding value of $\bar{\lambda}_S$ is calculated as $\bar{\lambda}_S = 1/T_R$. The four couples of values (PGA^{T_R} , $\bar{\lambda}_S$) are reported in a PGA

FIGURE 9 | Distribution along the height of the infilled frame for increasing PGA of: (a–c) maximum chord rotation demand in columns and beams averaged over 30 accelerograms, (d) maximum drift demand averaged over 30 accelerograms.

versus seismic hazard logarithmic coordinate system. According to CNR-DT 212/2013 [45], a quadratic function can be fitted to the relation between the seismic hazard and the PGA. The seismic performance is assumed suitable if the values of the mean annual frequency of exceedance λ obtained for the SD and NC limit states are lower than the limit values λ_{req} stipulated in the Italian technical document CNR-DT 212/2013 [45], which are 4.7×10^{-3} and 2.3×10^{-3} for SD and NC limit states, respectively, for existing class II (ordinary) buildings.

6 | Seismic Assessment of the Case Study Buildings and Identification of the e-CLT Configurations

Figure 9 shows the distribution along the height of the members' chord rotation and inter-storey drift ratio demand for the infilled building for increasing seismic excitations. Three values of PGA are considered: 0.05 g, corresponding to an almost elastic behavior, 0.20 g corresponding to a significant nonlinear behavior, and 0.35 g corresponding to a severe nonlinear behavior or incipient collapse. For each PGA, the maximum chord rotation demand averaged over the 30 accelerograms is reported (Figure 9a–c) for both ends of columns (red and pink dots and diamonds) and beams (black and grey dots and diamonds). In addition, the heightwise distribution of the maximum inter-storey drift ratio (average over 30 accelerograms) is shown in Figure 9d for the three values of PGA. In the case of moderate seismic input (0.05 g), the building behaves in a nearly elastic range and its response is mainly governed by the lateral stiffness, which is smaller for Y-frame model. As a consequence of this, chord rotation demands and inter-storey drifts of the Y-frame model are larger than those of X-frame model, but almost constant along the height in both models (Figure 9a). For higher seismic inputs, the maximum chord rotation demand and inter-storey drifts increase and the structural response becomes strongly nonlinear.

However, in X-frame model, a significant increase of the chord rotation demand is mainly observed at the columns ends of the third and fourth storey, while columns of other storeys and beams show a rate of increase significantly lower (Figure 9b,c). This indicates that damage is rather concentrated in the columns of third and fourth storeys. This is further confirmed by the inter-storey drift demands (Figure 9d), which are significantly larger in these storeys. Instead, in Y-frame model, chord rotation demand increases quite evenly among columns and beams of all storeys and the inter-storey drift demand shows a rather uniform distribution along the height. The different distributions of yielding in the two directions explain why the seismic response in X-direction is unexpectedly the most critical one. Indeed, in spite of the structure exhibiting the largest lateral stiffness in X-direction, the maximum chord rotation and inter-storey drifts turned out to be comparable, or even more demanding, than those in the Y-direction, due to the damage concentration under high earthquake intensities. It is notable that this conclusion could apply to most RC-framed buildings designed for gravity load only, which generally present beams stronger than columns in the frames arranged along the longitudinal direction. Indeed, even though not shown in any figures for the sake of brevity, the same conclusions can be extended also to the bare and the pilotis buildings. This further confirms that the analysis of the X- and Y-frame models, which exhibit different seismic responses, makes double the number of case studies of the parametrical analysis.

The structural response of the cases study suggests different ways to solve the seismic deficiencies of existing buildings. If the low seismic performance is caused by drift concentration and large chord rotation demands at few storeys, e-CLT could be used to increase strength and dissipation capacity of those storeys. Instead, if the demand is large, but uniformly distributed along the height, e-CLT can be introduced at all storeys to reduce uniformly the demand. Based on this observation, the following

	Spread e-CLT configuration		Local “extended” e-CLT configuration		Local “narrow” e-CLT configuration	
	Frame X1, X4	Frame Y1, Y8	Frame X1, X4	Frame Y1, Y8	Frame X1, X4	Frame Y1, Y8
Bare						
Infilled						
Pilotis						

FIGURE 10 | Configurations of e-CLT strengthening system, grey squares indicate the CLT panels.

configurations of e-CLT upgrading are proposed: (1) “spread” configuration, where the e-CLT system is introduced in every infilled span at all storeys; (2) “local” configuration, where the e-CLT system is introduced in every infilled span at selected storeys. On one side, the spread configuration represents the most conservative one, as it introduces the maximum number of e-CLT systems in the building façade. On the other side, the local configuration aims at introducing the minimum number of e-CLT systems to ensure that the structure fulfils the target limit state at the minimum cost. The local configuration is proposed into two variants, named the “narrow” and the “extended” local variants. In the “narrow” variant, the e-CLT system is introduced at the storey (or storeys) where the building experiences the largest drift demand. The goal of this configuration is to avoid that the e-CLT system is introduced at storeys where its dissipation capacity would be only slightly exploited because of the small drift demand. On one hand, the narrow local configuration is expected to promote yielding of the other storeys and to lead to a higher dissipation capacity of the structure. On the other hand, strengthening the storeys with the largest drift demand might lead to a shift of the maximum drift demand to the storeys adjacent to that (or those) where the e-CLT system has been introduced. Last but not least, the method of analysis used to determine the response of the frame (for instance, pushover analysis) may not be accurate in predicting exactly the storey where the largest demand occurs. For these reasons, the “extended” local variant has also been tested, wherein the e-CLT system is added also at the storeys immediately below and above that (or those) where the maximum drift demand is detected. Based on the collapse mechanisms and the seismic deficiencies provided by the nonlinear dynamic analysis of the unstrengthened case study, e-CLT system in the local narrow configuration was introduced at the fourth storey of the bare frame and the third storey of the infilled and pilotis frames. In the local extended configuration, the e-CLT was introduced in the third–fourth–fifth storey of the bare frame and in the second–third–fourth storey of the infilled and pilotis frame. Considering the seismic action along the Y-direction, the large drift demand involved not one, but three storeys (the second, third and fourth storeys of bare and infilled frame; the first, second and third storey of the pilotis frame) of the models. Hence, the local narrow configuration could not be strictly applied at one storey only, but it has to involve the three storeys with the largest displacement demand. As a consequence, the local extended configuration became coincident to the spread

configuration in the bare and infilled frame. Instead, in the pilotis frame, the local extended configuration included the first–second–third–fourth storeys. Finally, the spread configuration (i.e., e-CLT system introduced at all storeys) was analyzed for all X- and Y-frame models. Figure 10 shows both the spread and local seismic upgrading configurations.

The pushover analysis of each case study frame is carried out considering a load pattern proportional to the related first mode of vibration. The structural response at the attainment of NC limit state is observed in terms of distribution along the height of inter-storey drift demand. Even though it is shown only for the infilled building (Figure 11), all the analyzed X-frame models suffer from a concentration of drift demand at one or two storeys, while a more distributed drift demand is observed in the Y-frame models. Note that these results fit well with the structural response predicted by the IDA, thus confirming the pushover analysis as an effective and computationally affordable tool for the identification of the collapse mechanism of the building.

7 | Effect of the e-CLT on the Structural Response

Following the methodology presented in Section 5, a parametric analysis was run to pursue two objectives: to investigate the effect of e-CLT system on the structural response and to examine if and how the criteria adopted to locate the e-CLT system within the façade influenced the seismic response of the structure. To this end, all case study buildings were analyzed twice, that is before and after the introduction of the e-CLT system. For each frame, the three e-CLT configurations presented in Section 6 were considered. First, the seismic response of the case studies will be observed in terms of (1) fragility curves and (2) distribution along the height of D/C ratios of chord rotation and shear force in columns and beams. Hence, the assessment at NC and SD limit states will be summarized in terms of mean annual frequency of exceedance of the target limit states.

7.1 | Fragility Curves and Heightwise Distribution of Seismic Response

For the sake of clarity, first, the results of the infilled building are presented in detail. Figure 12a,b shows the fragility curves for NC limit state of the X- and Y-frame models of the unstrengthened

FIGURE 11 | Distribution along the height of drift demand of the unstrengthened infilled frames assessed by pushover analysis: (a) seismic forces along X-direction; (b) seismic forces along Y-direction.

FIGURE 12 | Fragility curves for NC limit state of the infilled building: (a) considering ductile only or ductile and fragile mechanisms of unstrengthened frame; (b) fragility curves of columns or beams of unstrengthened frame; (c) comparison between configurations without and with e-CLT.

infilled building. Fragility curves in Figure 12a are built aggregating the values of PGA leading to the NC limit state due to only ductile failures (red continuous line), or due to both ductile and fragile failure modes (black dashed line) in structural members. For both X- and Y-frame models, these two plots overlap. This means that fragile (shear) failure modes never occur before ductile ones, hence the considered limit state is attained due to ductile failure modes. In order to identify which structural member is responsible for the collapse, two more fragility curves (Figure 12b) are built aggregating the values of PGA corresponding to the attainment of NC limit state only in columns (red line) or only in beams (black dashed line). For both X- and Y-frame models, regardless of the input magnitude, columns lead to a larger probability of exceedance than beams and first attain the target limit state. Aggregating the minimum values of PGA determined for ductile and fragile failure modes in both beams and columns, the “critical” fragility curve of the frame is obtained. Hence, the PGA corresponding to the probability of exceedance of 50% (PGA capacity) is equal to 0.281 and 0.403 g (diamonds in Figure 12c) for the X- and Y-frame models (Table 4), respectively. This result

is consistent with the seismic response presented in Section 6. Indeed, damage concentration and large chord rotation demand mainly in columns are observed at the third storey of the X-frame model. Instead, a drift demand distributed among three storeys and chord rotation demand spread in both columns and beams of the Y-frame model is observed. Hence, despite the maximum displacement demands of X- and Y-frame models are similar, the collapse mechanism developed in the X-frame results to be less dissipative and leads to a PGA capacity that is about 30% lower than that of Y-frame (Table 4).

To investigate the effect of the e-CLT system on the seismic performance of the infilled frame models, the procedure is repeated for the seismically strengthened frames. Hence, Figure 12c compares the fragility curves of the unstrengthened frame (red line) with that of the frame with spread e-CLT configuration (black line), local extended e-CLT configuration (grey line), and local narrow e-CLT configuration (grey dashed line). The e-CLT system with spread configuration and the local extended configuration enhances the seismic performance of the infilled

TABLE 4 | Values of PGA corresponding to 50% probability of exceedance of NC limit state (PGA capacity).

Case study	Bare		Infilled		Pilotis	
	X-frames	Y-frames	X-frames	Y-frames	X-frames	Y-frames
Unstrengthened building	0.276 g	0.413 g	0.281 g	0.403 g	0.258 g	0.392 g
Spread e-CLT	0.368 g (+33%)	0.431 g (+4%)	0.347 g (+23%)	0.464 g (+15%)	0.361 g (+40%)	0.441 g (+13%)
Local e-CLT extended	0.358 g (+30%)	= spread	0.366 g (+30%)	= spread	0.364 g (+41%)	0.432 g (+10%)
Local e-CLT narrow	0.253 g (−8%)	0.454 g (+10%)	0.262 g (−7%)	0.448 g (+11%)	0.253 g (−2%)	0.402 g (+3%)

frame. In particular, the local extended configuration increases the PGA capacity by 30% and 15%, in the X- and Y-frame models, respectively. Note that, in the Y-frame model, the local extended configuration corresponds to the spread configuration. On the other hand, the local narrow configuration is less effective than the other configurations in the case of the Y-frame model (only an 11% increase in PGA capacity) and unexpectedly decreases the PGA capacity of the X-frame model with respect to that of the unstrengthened building.

To better understand the seismic performance of the infilled building, Figure 13 shows the seismic response along the height in terms of drift demand (Figure 13a), chord rotation D/C ratio of columns and beams (Figure 13b), and shear D/C ratio of columns and beams (Figure 13c). The values of the aforementioned engineering demand parameters are the maximum values averaged over the 30 accelerograms and refer to the PGA corresponding to 50% probability of exceedance of NC limit state of the unstrengthened frames. The heightwise distribution of the drift demand (Figure 13a) shows that the X-frame model in the unstrengthened configuration experiences a severe concentration of damage. The maximum drift demand is equal to 2.15% and 1.75% at fourth and third storey, respectively, while it is close to or lower than 1% at other storeys. Instead, in the case of the Y-frame model the maximum drift demand is almost 3%, but the distribution of drift demand is rather uniform along the height even though it was plotted for a higher value of PGA than X-frame. The same trend is observed also in terms of chord rotation D/C of columns. The e-CLT in the spread or local extended configuration reduces the maximum drift demand in the X-direction by 26% and 23%, respectively. In the Y-direction, the maximum drift reduces by 23% in the spread configuration (coincident with local extended configuration) and 26% in the local narrow configuration. It can be observed that the insertion of e-CLT in the spread or local extended configurations mainly affects the entity of the maximum drift demand and tends to regularize the shape of the distribution of drift demand along the height. The maximum chord rotation D/C ratio of columns at the storeys where the seismic demand was the largest decreases by about 24% for both X- and Y-frames. Indeed, the displacement demand at those storeys was large enough to activate the dampers, thus leading to a larger dissipative capacity and a reduction of the drift demand and chord rotation demand of columns. On the other side, where the drift demand was too low, (first and fifth storey in the X-frame model and first storey in the Y-frame model), the dampers could not activate and the e-CLT system does not modify the seismic response of those storeys. The seismic performance provided by the e-CLT system in the local narrow configuration results to be ineffective in the X-frame model, where e-CLT

system is introduced only at the third storey. In fact, in this case, the maximum drift demand at the third storey is significantly reduced (−71%), but it abruptly increases at the fourth storey, where it overcomes 3% (+48% with respect to the unstrengthened case). This behavior motivates the (apparently) unforeseen lower value of PGA capacity previously observed by fragility curves. In the Y-frame model, where the local narrow configuration involves three storeys, the e-CLT system reduces both the drift demand and the chord rotation demand of columns at those storeys on average by 17%, while those of other storeys increase. Hence, it improves the seismic performance and PGA capacity with respect to the unstrengthened case, even if its impact on the structural response is generally less significant than that of the other two configurations. With regards to the beams, when the drift demand is rather constant along the height, the e-CLT system decreases the chord rotation D/C ratio also of the beams at the storeys where the dampers effectively activate (Figure 13b). Although the fragility curves already identified the ductile failure of columns as the source of exceedance of the NC limit state in both X- and Y- models, for the sake of completeness, the D/C ratio in terms of shear in columns and beams is drawn in Figure 13c. The unstrengthened frame did not experience shear failure in any member, neither in the X- nor in the Y-frame model, and this result was not affected by the introduction of the e-CLT system, regardless of the configuration.

Also, in the case of the bare and pilotis buildings, the NC limit state is attained due to the ductile failure of columns in both X- and Y-frame models. Furthermore, the effect of e-CLT on the response of these frames is similar to that observed for the infilled frames. For the sake of brevity, only fragility curves built aggregating the results of all the verifications (ductile and fragile failure modes, beams and columns) are presented in Figure 14. The PGA capacities determined from fragility curves are reported in Table 4. For both bare and pilotis building (red plot), the unstrengthened X-frame model achieved a PGA capacity (Table 4) lower than that of the Y-frame counterpart. The e-CLT system introduced in the X-frame model (Figure 14a,b) according to both the spread and the local extended configurations increases the PGA capacity up to 33% and 40% in the bare and the pilotis frame, respectively. In the Y-frame model (Figure 14c,d), these two configurations of e-CLT have a lower impact on the value of PGA capacity. Indeed, the spread and the local extended configurations (note that in the case of bare frame, spread and local extended configurations are coincident) increase the PGA by 4% and about 10% in the bare and pilotis building, respectively. Also in the bare and pilotis building the local narrow configuration results to be the least effective one. Indeed, it leads the X-frame model to the NC limit state for a PGA lower than that of the unstrengthened

FIGURE 13 | Distribution along the height at the attainment of NC limit state in the unstrengthened infilled frame of (a) drift demand; (b) chord rotation D/C ratio of columns and beams; (c) shear force D/C ratio of columns and beams.

building, while in the Y-frame model, with respect to the other two e-CLT configurations, it provides a similar or a lower effect on the seismic response.

The distributions along the height of the unstrengthened bare and pilotis building of maximum drift demand, chord rotation D/C ratio in columns, and chord rotation D/C ratio in beams are plotted for the related PGA capacities in Figure 15a–c, respectively. The analysis of the drift demand and the chord rotation D/C ratio in columns shows that X-frame models of both bare and pilotis buildings in the unstrengthened configuration experienced concentration of damage at one or two storeys, while a seismic demand rather distributed along the height is observed in the Y-frame models. When applied in the spread or local extended configuration, the e-CLT system in the X-direction successfully reduced (by about 40%) both the drift demand and the chord rotation demand of columns of the storeys with the largest displacement demands. If e-CLT system is located according to the local narrow configuration, drift demand

and chord rotation demand in columns of the X-frame model concentrate at a single storey (the third in the bare building and the fourth in the pilotis building) and become even larger than those of the buildings in the unstrengthened configuration. This behavior stems from the fact that the e-CLT system was located only at the fourth storey in the bare building and the third storey in the pilotis building. Thus, the maximum seismic demand shift from these storeys to the adjacent ones, making the local narrow configuration not effective from a global point of view. In the Y-frame model, the local narrow configuration shows the least impact on the seismic response (about 15% reduction on maximum drift and chord rotation demands). With regards to beams, the e-CLT system leads to a reduction of the chord rotation demand in beams only in the Y-frame model (–36% and –43% with spread configuration in the bare and pilotis building, respectively), where the displacement demand was rather distributed along the height and the beams experienced a chord rotation demand comparable to that of columns (as shown in Figure 9).

FIGURE 14 | Fragility curves for NC limit state of the case study buildings before and after the introduction of e-CLT.

Generally speaking, in the strengthened *X*-frame models, especially in the case of infilled and pilotis building, the spread or local extended configurations (1) reduce the drift demand concentration that characterizes the response of the unstrengthened counterpart and (2) lead to an increased of the chord rotation demand in the columns of the storeys with lower drift demands, which are forced to participate in the dissipation process. Thanks to the larger number of RC members involved in the dissipative process and the additional contribution to the dissipative capacity provided by the dampers, the response of the frame is drastically reduced, and the PGA capacity is significantly enhanced. In the case of *Y*-frames, where damage is not localized at a few storeys even in the unstrengthened configuration, the e-CLT system reduces the chord rotation demand mainly thanks to the additional source of seismic energy dissipation given by the dampers, thus the benefit achieved by the frame is less remarkable.

7.2 | Mean Annual Frequency of Exceedance of Case Study Buildings at NC and SD Limit State

The seismic response of the analyzed case study buildings is also assessed in terms of mean annual frequency of exceedance of the NC and SD limit state considering the *X*- and *Y*-frame models. For all the considered cases, Figures 16 and 17 show the ratio of the mean annual frequency of exceedance λ of SD and NC limit states with respect to the relevant limit values λ_{req} required by [45]. If λ/λ_{req} overcomes unity, the corresponding verification is not fulfilled. The ratio λ/λ_{req} is evaluated considering the four aggregation rules considered for the construction of the fragility curves: only ductile failure modes in all members, both ductile and fragile failure modes in all members, or all failure modes only in columns or all failure modes only in beams. The

largest value among the four ratios is the one that quantifies the seismic performance of the frame. The red histogram refers to the building in the unstrengthened configuration, while the hatched histograms return the seismic performance achieved by the introduction of e-CLT in the local narrow (grey thin hatch), local extended (black thin hatch) and spread (black thick hatch) configurations. When seismic excitation acts in the *X*-direction (Figure 16), the building in the unstrengthened configuration is far from fulfilling either the NC or the SD limit state and shows values of λ/λ_{req} always much larger than 2.0. The e-CLT in the local narrow configuration increases the values of λ/λ_{req} , thus resulting in an ineffective intervention, which confirms the conclusions of Section 7.1. Consistently, e-CLT in both the spread and the local extended configurations significantly enhances the seismic performance of all the considered cases and decreases the value of λ/λ_{req} of the unstrengthened buildings by more than 50%. Furthermore, the full upgrading, that is the value of λ/λ_{req} rigorously lower than one, at both SD and NC limit states, is achieved for all the considered buildings when the e-CLT system is located according to the local extended configuration. In the case of seismic excitation acting in the *Y*-direction, the buildings in the unstrengthened configuration fulfill or are very close to fulfilling NC and SD limit state verifications. Anyway, the introduction of the e-CLT system leads in all the cases to a significant reduction of λ/λ_{req} , up to almost 46% with respect to the building in the unstrengthened configuration.

8 | Principles and Guidelines for a Design Procedure

Based on the results of the experimental tests and numerical investigation, a design procedure is proposed in this Section. The nonlinear static method of analysis, which is a well-known

FIGURE 15 | Distribution along the height at the attainment of NC limit state in the unstrengthened frame of (a) drift demand; (b) chord rotation D/C ratio of columns; (c) chord rotation D/C ratio of beams.

professional tool also allowed by seismic codes, is used for the prediction of the seismic response. In particular, the preliminary seismic assessment of the unstrengthened building can be performed by pushover analysis, which is able to estimate the collapse mechanism and the corresponding distribution along the height of the drift demand. Hence, the location of the e-CLT system can be determined. If the drift demand is concentrated at one storey (or a few storeys), the e-CLT system follows the local extended configuration. Instead, if the drift demand is widespread among the storeys, the e-CLT system can be located according to the spread configuration. At the selected storeys, the number and location of CLT panels depend on architectural features of the façade, particularly the number of spans without large openings.

At this stage of the design procedure, the activation force of the dampers is assumed equal to a reasonable value, for example,

that of the experimental test, and the stiffness of CLT panels is assumed infinite. Hence, a second pushover analysis is performed to assess the seismic response of the RC frame with the e-CLT systems so far designed. Given a target value of PGA, the corresponding seismic demand of the strengthened building is determined by nonlinear static methods of analysis (e.g., Capacity spectrum method or N2 method). If the target limit state has been overcome, the activation force of the damper has to be increased, so that the lateral strength of the strengthened building increases in turn. Eventually, the pushover analysis can be iteratively repeated until the strengthened building satisfies the target limit state.

After the activation force of the damper has been designed, the size of the CLT panel and the stroke of the damper can be determined to fulfill the drift demand at the target limit state. Specifically, to ensure that the dampers fully activate and

FIGURE 16 | Ratio of mean annual frequency of exceedance of X-frame models.

FIGURE 17 | Ratio of mean annual frequency of exceedance of Y-frame models.

dissipate energy, the in-plane stiffness of the CLT panel must be set large enough to minimize the deformation of the panel itself and turn the drift demand mainly into sliding displacement of the dampers. Hence, the CLT panel can be sized so that the horizontal relative displacement between its bottom and top sides induced by the activation force of the dampers is equal to a small rate of

the maximum drift demand at the target limit state. In turn, the stroke of the damper is set equal to the difference between the drift demand at the target limit state and the relative displacement between top and bottom sides of the panel. Since the CLT panels are expected to remain elastic during the seismic action, strength and stability of the panels have to be verified as well.

Once the e-CLT system has been fully designed (location, number, size of CLT panels, activation force, and stroke of the dampers), the structural response of the strengthened building can be assessed by pushover analysis. If the drift demand of the strengthened building at the target limit state still overcomes the capacity, the activation force and/or the size of the CLT panel can be increased.

With regards to the upper connections, these can be realized by conventional mechanical and/or chemical anchors widely available in the market. The connection can be designed as last step of the design procedure, to sustain (1) the vertical reaction force due to the self-weight of the CLT panel, plus (2) the horizontal reaction force that resists the activation force of the dampers, plus (3) the vertical reaction force that arises to balance the moment caused by the eccentricity between force transmitted by dampers and horizontal reaction force of connections. These forces are obtained from the three rigid body equilibrium equations of the CLT panel. The strength of the connections can be verified according to prescriptions available in seismic codes.

9 | Conclusions

The paper proposes the e-CLT system as a retrofit system suitable for an integrated energy and seismic approach to upgrading existing RC-framed building structures. The quasi-static experimental tests carried out on two full-scale one-storey one-bay RC infilled frames, without and with e-CLT, demonstrated that the retrofit system behaves under cyclic loading as planned. In particular, during the loading protocol, (1) the friction dampers, connecting the CLT panel to the RC beam, successfully activated and slid, (2) the CLT panel and the friction damper fastening system sustained the force delivered by the damper remaining in the elastic range of behavior, (3) the joint action of CLT panel and damper provided the RC frame with additional lateral stiffness, lateral strength and, even more, energy dissipation capacity. The activation of the damper occurred for the value of force assumed in design and its cyclic response was stable, without appreciable strength degradation even after many cycles of loading and unloading. At the end of the test, the damper did not exhibit evidence of yielding, local instabilities, or another kind of damage, thus configuring it as a damage-free device that does not need to be replaced even after a strong ground motion.

A numerical model of the RC infilled frame equipped with e-CLT system has been developed in OpenSees environment and calibrated based on the results provided by the experimental tests. A procedure based on a sub-component approach was established for the calibration of the model. The procedure led to the calibration of the parameters controlling the response of the components of the RC frame + e-CLT in subsequent steps. First, the mechanical properties assigned to the elements simulating the RC members are calibrated assuming as target the cyclic response, under large amplitude displacements, of the unstrengthened RC infilled frame (without e-CLT). In the second step, the parameters of infill panel are calibrated to fit the experimental response of the unstrengthened RC frame under low and intermediate amplitude displacements. In the third (final) step, the parameters that control the behavior of the CLT panel are calibrated based on the experimental response of the frame with

e-CLT. The cyclic response provided by the numerical models fits well the experimental response of both the unstrengthened and strengthened RC frame for low, intermediate, and large displacement cycles: elastic behavior, cracking of infill panels and subsequent lateral strength degradation, residual strength of RC frame + additional strength provided by e-CLT. Finally, running the numerical model requires a low computational burden, which makes it suitable to model multistorey buildings and perform extensive parametric investigations.

A parametric analysis was conducted on five-storey frames with three different configurations of infills (bare frame, with full height infills, and pilotis frame) and two different types of global nonlinear behavior (drift and chord rotation demand concentrated at few storeys or widespread along the height of the frame). The results allowed the quantification of the impact of the e-CLT system on the seismic response of realistic RC buildings and provided basic guidelines for the design of seismic upgrading by e-CLT. It was found that the effectiveness of the configuration of e-CLT is related to the global nonlinear behavior of the RC building to be strengthened. The local extended configuration (e-CLT introduced in the storey where the drift demand is maximum plus one storey below and one storey above) is suitable to upgrade RC framed buildings with a concentration of drift demand at a few storeys. Instead, if the drift demand is widespread along the height of the building, the spread configuration (e-CLT introduced at all storeys) should be preferred. The pushover analysis can predict the type of global nonlinear behavior of the building to be strengthened and, therefore, can be used to select the most appropriate configuration of e-CLT. The application of e-CLT on framed structures with concentration of demand led to an increase of PGA capacity by up to 40% and reduced the mean annual frequency of exceedance of the considered limit states by up to 74%. When e-CLT was used to upgrade framed structures with widespread seismic demand, the increase of PGA capacity and the decrease of mean annual frequency of exceedance of the considered limit states were up to 15% and 46%, respectively. The third configuration of retrofit, named local narrow configuration (e-CLT systems strictly introduced in the storey where the drift demand is maximum), resulted to be the least effective and somewhat detrimental. Indeed, on one side, the e-CLT system reduced the seismic demand at the storey where it was introduced but, on the other hand, shifted the seismic demand to the adjacent storeys, which experienced an abrupt and significant increase in the drift demand. Hence, the e-CLT system resulted to be a promising seismic upgrading technique and the parametric analysis conducted on realistic buildings confirmed this result. In the end, based on the experimental and numerical results, principles and steps to design seismic upgrading by e-CLT are provided.

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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